

PREMIERE Macro-regional All 100+ meeting -
Focus on Multi-actor proposal development challenges

Online, 9 February 2026

WHAT IS THIS OCCASIONAL PAPER?

Introduction to the PREMIERE macro-regional session

Four [Macro-regional Advisory Panels](#) (MRAPs), covering all of the EU and several associated countries, were established at the beginning of the PREMIERE project. Over 100 stakeholder panellists participate in the MRAPs, representing a diversity of sectors, roles and expertise levels in the MAA. The panellists themselves selected the three themes included in this occasional paper from a list of proposed novel topics for which knowledge and conceptualisation are only emerging for the MAA. These are the first three MA strategic themes for proposal development challenges.

What follows is a summary report of the reflections, ideas, good practices, and references discussed in three short (45-minute) online workgroups held on 9 February 2026. No further content has been developed after the meeting. Therefore, this occasional paper captures the raw knowledge generated to make it widely accessible. The workgroups also helped identify areas, notably AI, where PREMIERE can continue working in the future.

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1. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MA APPLICATIONS: FROM DESIGN, TO WRITING, AND AI ACTIVITIES IN THE WORK PLAN.

Generative Artificial Intelligence in the preparation of multi-actor project proposals

a. **Introduction: What is the European Commission's position on Generative AI and project proposal writing?**

Generative AI is now widely used to draft Horizon Europe proposals, and there is no doubt that it can greatly speed up and improve the quality of drafting. However, keep in mind that:

- There is a risk that misuse can create significant errors (e.g. hallucinations & hidden plagiarism), thereby generally damaging the credibility, reducing the quality, and potentially affecting the eligibility of proposals.
- When using AI in the drafting of multi-actor proposals, it is likely that specific attention is needed for respecting the necessary spirit of co-creation and practice-led innovation that is the basis of the multi-actor approach.

EC Guidelines (April 2025) on the *Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research*¹ have been published and are updated as a 'living document'. The EC position is clear: applicants may use generative AI tools to prepare Horizon Europe proposals, but humans are expected to stay in charge of content.

Basic good practice for AI use in proposal writing, identified by the EC, includes:

- Treat AI as an ASSISTANT, not a co-author! Core ideas, structure, key arguments, etc. should come from the consortium. AI can then be used to draft, refine and reorganise them.
- Apply strict QUALITY CONTROL! Always verify facts, references, and numbers/statistics. If available, run a plagiarism check.
- Carefully PROTECT confidentiality, IP and personal data.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2b6cf7e5-36ac-41cb-aab5-0d32050143dc_en

- Define a CLEAR WORKFLOW for the proposal writing team. In particular, agree within the team on where AI use is acceptable, and where it is not! Consistently iterate AI use with 'manual' review & editing. Clearly assign these editorial responsibilities from the outset.

Do not rely on AI! Remember that applicants remain fully responsible for every word submitted to the Portal in a proposal. Furthermore, AI use for proposal preparation must be transparent, with appropriate disclosure in Part B of the proposal that is submitted to the Portal.

b. Reflections / Learnings

This was the first time Generative AI had been discussed in the PREMIERE project and its macro-regional panels. The workshop session involved was an exploratory discussion and brainstorming on the theme of *"How to use AI to strengthen – not risk weakening – a multi-actor proposal?"*

c. Preliminary Reflections / Recommendations for Good Practice

Preliminary recommendations distilled from reflections/discussions in the short Workshop are:

- **Always respect the KEY REQUIREMENTS of the multi-actor approach!** Stay focused on upholding the principles and practices of the multi-actor approach. To preserve the authenticity of co-creation processes, prioritise genuine multi-actor involvement in proposal preparation and treat AI as a supportive assistant, not as a co-creator.
- **Build integrated workflows for your use of AI from the outset of proposal preparation.** Clearly assign tasks to your chosen AI tool(s) with a pre-agreed review of the resultant outputs by designated partners. Blend available technology with human oversight, but remember that partners' knowledge will always be most critical. Carefully double-check all AI outputs to i) avoid the core risks of over-reliance or misuse by individual partners, and ii) guard against the known dangers of hallucinations and plagiarism. Always verify facts, respect

privacy and IP issues, and don't forget that human-crafted narratives will always be the most convincing!

- **Use AI to make the multi-actor participatory/co-creation processes undertaken during proposal preparation much more apparent and compelling to evaluators.** For example, amplify your evidence of multi-actor participation in proposal writing by using AI to map and visualise the multi-actor and other relevant participatory processes you have utilised.
- **Strategically disclose your use of AI.** Build evaluators' trust through transparency and by explicitly stating how AI was used in the proposal preparation process. Highlight that your use of AI complemented – never replaced – co-creation during the drafting of your proposal.
- **Use AI for checking the structure and internal logic of your multi-actor approach.** Employ AI to cross-check the consistency and coherence of the logic and content of your multi-actor proposal against the official multi-actor requirements, plus any specific indications about the required multi-actor approach in the topic text. For example, simulate the evaluation of your proposal by prompting your AI tool(s) with the known criteria for evaluating multi-actor proposals. This can provide a "fresh perspective" on the proposal, spotting potential flaws when partners are otherwise too immersed in the small details of the text.
- **Strengthen your multi-approach proposal by empowering your partners to contribute to the writing process with the assistance of AI.** Numerous AI tools can be very effectively used to make the proposal preparation process more 'accessible' to your partners. For example, by bridging gaps in technical/social understanding amongst consortium partners or by refining the inputs of non-native English speakers.

2. BALANCING THE DESIGN PROCESS IN MA PROPOSALS BETWEEN RESEARCH-TECHNICAL AND PRACTICE-COMMUNITY PARTNERS.

How to authentically embed in practice the Multi-Actor Approach across the full project lifecycle – from consortium design through evaluation and monitoring.

a. Reflections / Learnings

- **Knowledge of the intricacies of Horizon Europe Projects**

- Horizon Europe projects are complex and intimidating for new entrants, particularly for practice-oriented organisations not historically involved in research funding.
- New institutions are strongly advised to partner first before leading, in order to build familiarity with processes, obligations and consortium dynamics.
- The administrative burden of Horizon Europe is a significant deterrent for practitioner partners; many fear being overloaded with reporting and compliance obligations.

- **Paper and practice**

- There is a persistent gap between what is written in project proposals and what actually happens on the ground. Multi-Actor Approach can look convincing on paper while remaining tokenistic in practice.
- The use of AI to generate narratives around MAA has heightened concerns about the authenticity of commitments made at the proposal stage.
- Evidence of genuine practitioner engagement, beyond deliverables and reports, is difficult to assess through current evaluation mechanisms.
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- **Bridging research and business**

- Researchers and businesses operate in divergent worlds: researchers pursue knowledge extension; businesses seek quick, applicable solutions. Bridging these requires deliberate co-design from the outset.
- Proposals that originate exclusively within research institutions make it difficult for other actors to meaningfully shape the conceptual framework. Early, multi-profile involvement from the idea stage is considered the most effective model.

- Practitioner partners should be encouraged to develop a clear 'package' – articulating what they offer and what value participation holds for their own organisation – rather than positioning themselves as add-ons.

- **Mutual understanding between different stakeholders**
 - Trust-building is central to effective multi-actor consortia. This requires ongoing engagement, not just formal review meetings, and a genuine willingness to hand over responsibility to less established partners.
 - Stakeholder mapping is a valuable tool for identifying partner influence and impact, and for making strategic, evidence-based decisions about consortium composition.
 - Researchers who already work across the research-practice divide (e.g., those with farming or industry backgrounds and working in research) are particularly effective at bridging the gap and modelling good practice.

- **Administrative burden in Horizon projects**
 - The administrative demands of Horizon Europe projects fall disproportionately on lead partners, particularly universities, whose internal procurement and compliance processes can significantly hamper activities like cascading funding to community actors.
 - Practitioner partners often participate without financial cover for time spent on activities beyond their contracted deliverables, limiting the depth of engagement.
 - Co-leadership of work packages or tasks is proposed as a practical way to reduce perceived administrative burden for newcomers while giving them meaningful agency within the project.

- **Practitioner involvement in projects**
 - Not all practitioner partners are equally motivated: some engage primarily for visibility, funding, or box-ticking within their own organisations. Lead partners must be discerning in distinguishing genuine from performative engagement.
 - Practitioners with prior project experience should leverage that track record actively, presenting previous involvement and articulating how they wish to step up, including into co-leadership roles.

- Brokerage events, such as those facilitated by PREMIERE, are effective in enabling practitioners to pitch their value proposition and connect with academic leads actively seeking partners.
- **Evaluation and monitoring & the role of the Commission**
 - Evaluation of MAA occurs at two distinct stages: (1) assessment of project proposals, and (2) monitoring of ongoing projects. Both stages were identified as insufficiently equipped to identify tokenistic versus authentic multi-actor engagement.
 - Evaluators themselves hold varying interpretations of what constitutes a credible Multi-Actor Approach, leading to inconsistent scoring and feedback.
 - The Commission is seen as under-utilising its leverage over universities and research institutions: stronger, clearer expectations, including around funding flows and accountability, could drive genuine structural change.
 - Review meetings should be more than administrative checkpoints; they should serve as genuine consortium health checks where all partners, including practitioners, are heard and contribute to direction-setting.

b. Best practices / Examples

- **Early, multi-profile co-design:** Starting the proposal development process with at least two to three people from different profiles (researcher, practitioner, intermediary) from the very beginning significantly improves the authenticity and quality of the MAA.
- **Stakeholder mapping:** Develop a structured stakeholder mapping approach, assessing partner influence versus impact. This informed strategic partner selection and ethics monitoring throughout the project lifecycle
- **Ethics as a monitoring tool:** Using the ethics work package not as a compliance obligation but as an embedded monitoring and evaluation mechanism, including open feedback platforms (open diaries) and ambassador networks, to continuously assess partner inclusion and voice.

- **Practitioner pitching:** Encouraging practice partners to prepare a structured 'package' of what they offer, enabling them to be active participants in consortium building rather than passive recruits.
- **Networking grants:** Enterprise Ireland provides grants (up to approx. €12,000) to support networking with potential partners before and during proposal development – a model other national and regional systems in Europe could consider if not already in place².
- **Field-based evaluation:** Evaluators going into the field (observing, talking to partners, and assessing real-world impact) rather than relying solely on written deliverables.
- **Geographically distributed consortia:** Deliberately seeking partners across different European regions (north, south, east, west) and delegating the identification of local practitioner partners to each national partner, reducing the burden on the lead partner.

c. References / Further materials

- ❖ **PREMIERE Project resources:** Toolkits, brokerage event materials, and guidance on multi-actor engagement available on the PREMIERE website and LinkedIn page.
[PREMIERE MULTIACTOR](#) · [PREMIERE AT LINKEDIN](#)
Including: [PREMIERE's Multi-Actor Inclusion and Stakeholder Engagement Checklist](#)
- ❖ **European Commission partner search portal:** The Horizon Europe portal maintains a register of organisations and groups seeking project partnerships – a useful starting point for consortium building.
[EU Funding & Tenders Portal](#) · [Partnering | EURAXESS](#) · [Home | Horizon Europe NCP Portal](#)
- ❖ **Enterprise Ireland networking grant:** Funding to support pre-proposal networking and partnership development (Ireland-specific; circa €12,000 maximum). Check for equivalent schemes in other member states.
[Enterprise Ireland's Horizon Europe Funding Supports | Horizon Europe](#)

² PREMIERE is currently preparing a public report on seed-funding for multi-actor proposal development to be released during 2026.

- ❖ **EIP-AGRI (European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability):** Referenced as a prior model of multi-actor approach, with lessons on the risks of superficial farmer engagement and tick-box compliance.

[About EIP-AGRI projects | EU CAP Network](#)

3. CASCADE-FUNDING (FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO THIRD PARTIES) IN MA TOPICS

a. Introduction

(Robert Carroll, F6S Network contributed as expert for this session)

FSTP (Financial Support to Third Parties), often referred to as cascade funding or open calls, is a mechanism in Horizon Europe (especially Cluster 6) for distributing funds to third parties outside the core consortium. Its primary purpose is to achieve a "boots on the ground" effect, enabling projects to reach practitioners such as farmers, foresters, and small SMEs who may not have the capacity to be full project partners but are essential for testing, validation, and agile innovation.

Number of 2026 MA Call Topics suggesting Financial Support for Third Parties as topics by project type (RIA, IA, CSA) (11 / 23 – 48%)

Summary of calls in Horizon 2026 Work Programme (Cluster 6 and Soil), suggesting FSTP.

b. Reflections / Learnings

A common myth is that FSTP satisfies all multi-actor (MA) requirements. In reality, it is a support tool and must be integrated with other measures; it does not replace the need for core partner engagement. FSTP often starts later in a project (e.g., month 18), but practitioner perspectives are needed from the beginning to ensure the project isn't an "ivory tower" exercise. FSTP should be "intimately interwoven" with the proposal's substance rather than appearing as an optional "plug-in" or "add-on".

- A critical piece of advice provided was to look at the cascade funding requirements first and **work backwards to design the project**. The mistake many applicants make is gathering a group of partners first and then trying to "fit" FSTP into the structure, which often leads to a proposal that lacks cohesive logic and fails to implement FSTP properly. While FSTP has its own specific KPIs, they must be complementary to the overall thrust of the proposal to ensure it is a unified effort.
- FSTP should not just be a budget line but a way to demonstrate a "greater degree of ambition" in terms of innovation levels and deployment scope. It is expected to be a tool that significantly **maximizes the impact of the project** outcomes. FSTP should be viewed as the "vehicle" or "vessel" that allows the consortium to transport its results out of the "consortium bubble" and into the real world. It should be embedded in the "Excellence" section of the proposal as part of the overall methodology for testing, validation, and agile innovation.
- The "interwoven" nature is also demonstrated by the timing and clarity of the calls. For instance, in some Mission-related calls, the first cascade call is expected to be launched **within the first 12 months**, requiring the FSTP logic to be fully matured and operational from the very start of the project.
- Proposals must adhere precisely to the call text regarding **budget limits** (e.g., if it indicates "up to 2 million," evaluators will expect that amount) and the specific number/type of open calls requested. While FSTP is 100% funded, Robert and Margit noted that selecting the right partner to hold the budget is critical. In Innovation Actions, for-profit partners usually have a 70% funding rate, and there can be confusion or complications if they are the ones distributing 100%-funded FSTP grants. Robert recommends using a non-profit entity within the group to handle these funds to simplify the financial management.
- Applicants often underestimate the **administrative burden, legal complexity, and financial risks** associated with managing FSTP. Managing these open calls is essentially running a mini-funding program within a larger project.

- Managing FSTP now requires a full, **dedicated work package**. This includes managing the entire lifecycle of the call: from launching the platform to organising expert evaluators (who must be paid from the project budget) and conducting account validations. Robert emphasised the necessity of a dedicated IT platform to link application systems with the EU's Funding and Tenders portal, as well as the effort required to disseminate the call effectively to reach the right applicants.
- The legal burden involves creating and **managing subgrantee contracts** between the FSTP manager and the third parties that define the rules of engagement and stage payments. Running these calls effectively requires a specialised legal and financial team. By having a specialised entity handle the contracts, the legal burden is taken off the coordinator, who may be wary of signing agreements with numerous small entities across different countries. Large public institutions and universities are often not equipped to handle the agility required to move FSTP funds. Their financial offices may struggle with the administrative task of processing and moving millions of euros to third parties outside the consortium.
- A major risk is that the **consortium remains responsible** to the Commission for the implementation of the sub-projects. If a third party fails to deliver or goes bankrupt, the responsibility and potential financial reduction of the grant falls on the consortium.

c. Best practices / Examples

It is advisable to involve a partner with a dedicated **IT platform for FSTP calls** and legal/financial **team experienced** in running open calls.

The partner managing the FSTP budget should ideally be a **non-profit** or public entity with a 100% funding rate to avoid the need for matching funds on the distributed amounts.

- The "Foody" project was cited as a successful example of using FSTP for AI digital services for food data.

Example: <https://foodity.eu/>

- The Foody project was a Horizon Europe Cluster 6 initiative specifically focused on AI digital services for food data.
- The project was designed to deliver data-driven solutions for the food sector. Its work plan included piloting, mentoring, demonstrations, and technical development.

- It utilized a specialized IT platform to manage the lifecycle of its open calls, linking application systems directly with the [European Commission's Funding and Tenders portal](#).
- Foody has recently closed its calls, demonstrating the practical application of distributing third-party funding to support innovative AI applications outside the core project consortium.

d. References / Further materials

The Commission published an [official guidance on FSTP](#) to clarify rules:

Additional information sources:

- [general-mga_horizon-euratom_en.pdf](#)
- [aga_en.pdf](#)
- [Frequently asked questions on financial support to third parties \(FSTP\) within EU cooperation](#). European Commission. 2023.
- FAQs at the Funder and Tenders portal. Use “FSTP” or “Financial Support to Third Parties” for a selection of answered questions at the portal.

On strengthening MA proposal development challenges

This short occasional paper is another example on how PREMIERE itself uses the MA Approach, in this case in collaboration with the macro-regional stakeholder panels to strengthen MA proposal preparation.

Would you like to contribute with other ideas in the three themes presented, or suggest new emerging challenges to be addressed? Contact us: jordi@highclere-consulting.org

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